

Enrichment of Tarhana with Olive Leaf Powder: Evaluation of Physical, Functional, Powder, and Sensory Properties

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Abstract

Olive leaves are a by-product of olive cultivation and remain underutilized despite their significant potential as a rich source of health-promoting and functional components. Similarly, tarhana, a fermented food product, is known for its valuable nutritional properties. This study aimed to combine these two beneficial products by examining the effect of different concentrations of dried olive leaf powder (0, 2.5, 5, 7.5, and 10% by weight) on the physical, functional, powder, and sensory properties of tarhana samples. Results showed that moisture content of the tarhana samples were below 10% (wet basis, wb). The ash content (2.17-2.71%, wb) and water holding capacity (32.50-59.00%) of samples increased significantly with the addition of olive leaf powder ($p < 0.05$). The pH value of the doughs was found to be around 5.5 and decreased during the fermentation. The wettability and solubility times of all samples were found to be less than 25 seconds and 16 seconds, respectively. All tarhana samples exhibited high flowability and low stickiness properties. Formulations containing up to 7.5% olive leaf powder were well-received by consumers.

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1. Introduction

Olive leaves (OL) are a significant agricultural by-product derived from both pruning olive trees and processing olives at mills. These residues account for approximately 10% of the total weight of olives delivered to mills (Rosello-Soto et al., 2015). Olive leaves are a rich source of polyphenolic compounds and other beneficial phytochemicals, including flavonoids and triterpenes (Abaza et al., 2015; Markhali et al., 2020). It has been demonstrated in studies that olive leaves exhibit antioxidant activity (Lee et al., 2010), possess anti-HIV properties (Khattab et al., 2016), have antiproliferative and apoptotic effects (Katsoulieiris, 2016), show lipid-lowering activity (Afify et al., 2018), and exhibit additional beneficial properties. In addition, olive leaf extract, widely used in traditional and natural remedies, is known for its ability to boost energy levels, reduce blood pressure, and support both the cardiovascular and immune systems and possessing antimicrobial qualities. Like several natural items, the extract's composition can vary based on factors such as geographical location, plant cultivar, and agricultural conditions (Borjan et al., 2020).

A drying process is applied to olive leaves to extend their shelf life and enable their use in food formulations. Olive leaves or their extract are dried using various methods, including sun (Yateem et al., 2014), shade (Ghelichkhani et al., 2019), hot air (Erbay and Icier, 2009; Cárcel et al., 2010; Ahmad-Qasem et al., 2016), microwave (Elhussein and Sahin, 2018), oven (Elhussein and Sahin, 2018; Afaneh et al., 2015), freeze (Kashaninejad et al., 2020), spray (Kiritsakis et al., 2018), and vacuum drying (Şahin et al., 2018; Elhussein and Sahin, 2018). Olive leaves are considered an active component in the food sector for food fortification and packaging. Olive leaves are available on the market, including dried whole leaves for herbal tea, powders derived from dried plants, liquid extracts, tablets, and nutritional products. Among these, the use of dried whole olive leaves as tea has garnered

particular interest from consumers (Mumcu, 2023; Özcan and Matthäus, 2017). In many studies, olive leaves or their extracts have been added to olive oil to enhance its quality and nutritional values (Bouaziz et al., 2010; Malheiro et al., 2013; Tarchoune et al., 2019). Furthermore, studies on Taralli (Cedola et al., 2020), pasta (Conti et al., 2023), sponge cake (Ataei and Hojjatoleslamy, 2017), minced beef meat (Aouidi et al., 2017), poultry (Saleh et al., 2020), sheep cheese (Bolletta et al., 2022), and low-alcohol light beer (Cappelin et al., 2024) enriched with olive leaves or their extract to increase nutritional value have also been encountered.

A traditional Turkish fermented product, tarhana is produced with a blend of yogurt, wheat, and various vegetables. It has a lot of B vitamins, minerals (Mg, Ca, K, etc.), organic acids, and free amino acids. Regarding its nutritional value, tarhana is regarded as a nutritious product suitable for feeding elderly people or children in Türkiye (Tekgül et al., 2021; Çalışkan Koç et al., 2021; Kilci and Gocmen, 2014). Additionally, the fermentation process of tarhana enhances its fatty acid profile, which may assist in lowering the levels of LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol and promote heart health, making tarhana advantageous for cardiovascular well-being (Yavuz et al., 2024; Tekgül et al., 2021; Çalışkan Koç et al., 2021). In our study, we combined olive leaf powder and tarhana, both known for their significant health benefits. As far as we know, no research investigations have been done with the application of olive leaf powder as an ingredient in tarhana formulations. Consequently, this study aims to investigate the effect of different amounts of dried olive leaf powder on the physical, functional, powder, and sensory properties of tarhana samples.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Materials

All ingredients (wheat flour (Söke Mill. Ind. and Trd. Inc.), full-fat yogurt (Ak Food Ind. and Trd. Inc.), onion, tomato paste (Olca Food Ind. and Trd. Inc.), bakers' yeast (Yuva Food Ind. and Trd. Inc.), salt (Safir Ind. and Trd.

Inc.), water (Damla Ind. and Trd. Inc.), mint, and red paprika (Avşarlar Ind. and Trd. Inc.) were purchased from a local market in Alanya, Antalya, Türkiye.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Drying of olive leaves

Olive leaves used in the study were collected from Alanya, Antalya, Türkiye. The leaves were washed, excess water removed, and dried in a convection oven (Memmert UN110, Schwabach, Germany) at 65 °C for 6h. The dried olive leaves was ground using a grinder (Premier, PRG259, Türkiye), converted into powder form, and stored in a glass jar at 4 °C until further analyzed.

2.2.2. Tarhana production

Tarhana samples were produced following the methods specified by Çalışkan Koç and Özçira (2019) and Kömürcü and Bilgiçli (2020). Olive leaf powder ratios (0, 2.5, 5, 7.5, and 10% by weight) were determined based on the preliminary tests and it was decided that the maximum limit would be 10%. Additionally,

tarhana without olive leaf powder (0%) was produced and named as a control. Olive leaf powders were incorporated into the tarhana dough by substituting a portion of the wheat flour. The tarhana dough was incubated at 30 ± 2 °C for 72 hours. The dough was kneaded manually every 24 hours during fermentation. Once fermentation was complete, the tarhana dough was dried in a convective oven (Memmert, UF 110, Germany) at 50 ± 2 °C with a 20% air ventilation rate. The drying process continued until the moisture content of the tarhana samples was reduced to 10%. The drying times for the tarhanas containing 0%, 2.5%, 5%, 7.5%, and 10% olive leaf powder were 20, 19, 17, 16, and 16 hours, respectively. The dried tarhana pellets were then ground into a powder using a kitchen blender (1000 W power, SHB 3107, Sinbo, Türkiye). To ensure uniform particle size, the resulting powder was sifted through a 1 mm sieve. The tarhana samples were produced in two replicates and the formulations are presented in Table 1. The steps involved in tarhana production are illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 1. Formulation of tarhana

Ingredient (g)	Control	TOLP-2.5	TOLP-5	TOLP-7.5	TOLP-10
Wheat flour	500	487.5	475	462.5	450
Olive leaf powder	0	12.5	25	37.5	50
Yogurt	250	250	250	250	250
Onion	120	120	120	120	120
Tomato paste	60	60	60	60	60
Bakers' yeast	10	10	10	10	10
Salt	40	40	40	40	40
Mint	10	10	10	10	10
Paprika	10	10	10	10	10

Control: Tarhana with 0% olive leaf powder; TOLP-2.5: Tarhana with 2.5% olive leaf powder; TOLP-5: Tarhana with 5% olive leaf powder; TOLP-7.5: Tarhana with 7.5% olive leaf powder; TOLP-10: Tarhana with 10% olive leaf powder

Figure 1. Tarhana production

2.2.3. Analysis

2.2.3.1. Physical analysis

The moisture, ash content, and pH of olive leaf powder, wheat flour, and tarhana samples were determined. The American Association of Cereal Chemists AACC (2000) method was used for the determination of the moisture (No. 44–01) and ash (No. 08–01) contents of the samples. The pH values of the sample were measured using a pH meter (SevenExcellence S 400 Mettler Toledo AG, China). The change in pH value of tarhana dough during fermentation was monitored.

2.2.3.2 Functional analysis and powder properties

The water oil holding capacity (WHC) analysis was performed according to Stone et al. (2015). Wettability and solubility times, and dispersibility values were determined based on the methods described by Gong et al. (2008), Goula and Adamopoulos (2008) and Jinapong et al. (2008), respectively. Bulk and tapped density values were measured and Carr Index (CI) and Hausner Ratio (HR) values were calculated following the method of Jinapong et al. (2008).

2.2.3.3 Sensory evaluation

Tarhana samples containing olive leaf powder were prepared as soup following the method described by Çalışkan Koç and Özçira

(2019). Sensory analysis was conducted with 20 students from the Culinary Program at Alanya University. Along with the soup, bread, and water were provided to the participants. The sensory evaluation included color, odour, consistency (both on the spoon and in the mouth), homogeneity, flavor, foreign flavor, and overall acceptability. Scores for these attributes were recorded and analyzed.

2.2.3.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 20.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). A one-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) and Duncan's multiple range test ($\alpha=0.05$) were applied. The tarhana samples were produced in duplicate, and all analyses were performed in triplicate.

3. Results and Discussion

In this study, fresh olive leaves collected from Alanya were dried and incorporated into the tarhana formulation, a traditional Turkish fermented food product, by substituting wheat flour with olive leaf powder. All tarhana samples were successfully produced, demonstrating the feasibility of this approach. The physical, functional and powder properties of the tarhana samples were thoroughly examined, and their sensory acceptability was evaluated by a panel of participants.

3.1. Results of physical and functional analysis

Physical and functional analyses applied to tarhana samples were also applied to olive leaf powder and wheat flour. The moisture and ash contents, pH, and WHC values of the olive leaf powders were measured as 4.57% (wb), 8.09% (wb), 6.89, and 275.01%, respectively. The moisture and ash contents, pH, and WHC values of the wheat flour were measured as 12.76% (wb), 0.68% (wb), 6.09, and 55.65%, respectively. According to the results, it can be said that olive leaf powder has lower moisture content, and higher ash content, pH and WHC values compared to wheat flour. Moisture content is a crucial factor, as it directly affects the shelf life of foods. Similar to our results, the moisture content values (3.39-6.37%) have been reported for leaves dried using different methods (at room temperature drying, drying at 105 °C, and freeze drying) (Cör Andrejč et al., 2022). The ash content of olive leaf powder (8.09%, wb) was slightly higher than the values reported by Cavalheiro et al. (2015) who studied olive leaves from five cultivars and found ash content values ranging from 4.37% to 6.00% (wb). This variation may be attributed to differences in the olive leaf cultivars. Olive leaf powders were mixed with water (1:10 wt%), and the pH of the resulting aqueous solution was measured to assess its impact on the pH of the tarhana. The WHC of olive leaf powder was also evaluated, as this property is significant for its potential use in complex food formulations.

The moisture content of the tarhana samples ranged from 6.28% to 8.40% (wb, Table 2). The addition of olive leaf powder significantly increased the moisture content of the tarhana compared to the control ($p < 0.05$). This increase may be attributed to the high water-holding capacity (WHC) of olive leaf powder (275.01%) compared to wheat flour (55.65%). Except for the control and the tarhana containing 5% olive leaf powder, no significant differences were observed in the moisture content of the other samples ($p > 0.05$). The shorter drying time of the tarhana samples with olive leaf powders,

compared to the control, may also explain the higher moisture content values. The moisture content of all samples is below the 10% value specified in the Turkish standard (Anon, 2004) and can be said to comply with the legal limits. Similarly, Çalışkan Koç and Özçira (2019) reported that the addition of wheat germ to the tarhana formulation resulted in an increase in the moisture content values of the samples due to the high WHC of wheat germ (61.00 %) than wheat flour (53.33%). Aktaş and Akın (2020) also reported that an increase in the amount of rice and corn brands (5-15%) increased the moisture content values of the tarhana samples, nevertheless, this rise was found insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

Tanguler and Tatlısoy (2022) evaluated the use of shalgam residue (0–150 g) as a partial substitute for wheat flour (1000–850 g) in tarhana production and reported that the ash content of tarhana samples ranged from 5% (control) to 6.44% (maximum shalgam residue substitution). The increase in ash content was attributed to the higher ash content of shalgam residue compared to wheat flour. Similarly, Akan and Özdeştan-Ocak (2021) investigated the influence of grape seed extract (GSE) on tarhana properties and found that the ash content ranged from 1.2% to 1.9% (wb) in samples prepared with 0 g kg⁻¹, 4 g kg⁻¹, 8 g kg⁻¹, and 16 g kg⁻¹ replacement of wheat flour with GSE. Their findings indicated that the ash content of tarhana is unaffected by fermentation but significantly increases with GSE addition ($p < 0.05$) due to the higher ash content of GSE. In our study, the ash content of tarhana samples ranged from 2.17% (control) to 2.71% (TOLP-10, Table 2). Similar to the findings of Tanguler and Tatlısoy (2022) and Akan and Özdeştan-Ocak (2021), the ash content of our tarhana samples increased significantly with the addition of olive leaf powder ($p < 0.05$). This increase can be attributed to the high ash content of olive leaf powder (8.09%, wb) compared to wheat flour (0.68% wb). These results reinforce the conclusion that the addition of high-ash-content ingredients, such as olive leaf powder, shalgam residue, or GSE, significantly amplifies the ash content of tarhana.

According to Bozkurt and Gürbüz (2008), tarhana has pH values between 3.3 and 5.0, which has a bacteriostatic impact on pathogenic microorganisms. For this reason, tarhana doughs were left to fermentation for three days until the pH value decreased to 5 and below. Changes in the pH value of tarhana samples are shown in Figure 2. During the fermentation, the tarhana doughs were kneaded every day and the sample was taken and the pH value was checked. The pH value of the doughs (0. day) was found to be around 5.5 and this value decreased during the

fermentation. The highest pH value was observed in the control sample and the lowest pH value was observed in tarhana dough containing 10% olive leaf powder. Increased microbial activity at higher olive leaf powder amounts may be related to this situation. Similar findings were also observed by Aktaş and Akın (2020). An increase in the pH value of tarhana was observed with the drying process. It can be said that this situation is caused by the evaporation of some organic acids with drying.

Figure 2. Changes in pH value of tarhana samples during fermentation time

3.2. Functional and powder properties

Tarhana is a fermented powder soup known by different names in Türkiye and many other countries. Consumers desire quick, easy, and complete dissolution of tarhana in water and easy flow without sticking to the packaging material. In this context, reconstitution behavior and flow properties of tarhana samples were examined, and the results are given in Table 2. One crucial functional characteristic of viscous meals is their ability to hold water (Ertaş et al., 2015). Tarhana's ability to retain water is determined by structural proteins and starch (Hayta et al., 2002). The WHC values of tarhanas increased in proportion to the increasing amount of olive leaf powder ($p < 0.05$). The high WHC of olive leaf powder (275.01%) can be explained as the reason for this situation. It can also be said that there is a direct proportional relationship

between the moisture content of the samples and the WHC. Çalışkan-Koç and Özçira (2019) reported that WHC of tarhana samples ranged from 45.17 (control) to 23.00 (50% wheat flour–50% wheat germ substitution). The addition of wheat germ significantly reduced the WHC of tarhana, which the researchers attributed to the larger particle size of wheat germ compared to wheat flour, as well as its protein content and chemical composition. In contrast, Şensoy and Tarakçı (2023) found that the almond ratio added to tarhana had no statistically significant effect on WHC ($p > 0.05$). They suggested that the lack of impact on WHC might be due to the almond's low starch content, which influences water retention. They also noted that the WHC of fiber is influenced by its chemical and physical structure, processing, and soluble dietary fiber content. In our study, the addition

of olive leaf powder significantly increased the WHC of tarhana, rising from 32.50% in the control to 59.00% in the tarhana containing 10% olive leaf powder. This increase may be attributed to the leafy structure and higher WHC of olive leaf powder compared to wheat flour. The results demonstrate that the structural and chemical properties of added ingredients, such as olive leaf powder, wheat germ, or almond pulp, play a critical role in determining the WHC of tarhana formulations. The dispersibility values of tarhana samples ranged from 15.80% to 28.19%. While these values are relatively low, it is important to note that tarhana is typically prepared by boiling, and the use of room-temperature water during the analysis, rather than boiling, likely accounts for the lower dispersibility values observed. As the amount of olive leaf powder increased, the dispersibility values of tarhana samples decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$). Similar trends were reported by Çalışkan-Koç and Özçira (2019), who observed a decrease in dispersibility values (31.43%–84.56%) with the addition of wheat germ. The researchers attributed this reduction to the high oil content of wheat germ, while also noting that dispersibility values could improve at higher preparation temperatures. Conversely, Dadalı (2023) found that the addition of artichoke bracts (*Cynara scolymus* L.) improved the dispersibility of tarhana samples, with values increasing from 14.28% (control) to 82.67% (T-30). The dispersibility of tarhana is significantly influenced by the type and amount of added ingredients. While high oil or fiber content, such as in olive leaf powder and wheat germ, reduces dispersibility, ingredients like artichoke bracts can enhance it. Moreover, preparation conditions, such as higher temperatures, are crucial for improving dispersibility in practical applications. The control and tarhana samples containing olive leaf powder were wetted in water for less than 25 s. Although the wettability time of the samples increased as the amount of olive leaf powder increased, this time was found to be statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). All tarhana samples were dissolved in water in a short time (< 16 s). Contrary to the wettability results, the

samples dissolved in water faster as the amount of olive leaf powder increased. Dadalı (2023) reported a statistically significant increase in wettability times with the addition of artichoke bracts, where wettability times ranged from 25.35s for the control sample to 306.10s for the T30 formulation ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, Çalışkan-Koç and Özçira (2019) observed wettability times of wheat germ-enriched tarhana samples to be less than 70s, which were attributed to the particle size and composition of wheat germ. Conversely, Erdoğan and Çalışkan-Koç (2021) reported significantly higher wettability times in commercial gluten-free tarhana with the lowest moisture content and WHC ($p < 0.05$). They suggested that the difficulty of water diffusion inside particles with lower moisture content was a contributing factor. However, these wettability times could be significantly reduced by incorporating gluten-free legume flours ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the solubility times of commercial gluten-free flours and legume-cereal flour tarhana samples were reported to be below 60s. In line with previous studies, our results confirm that ingredient composition and moisture content significantly influence wettability and solubility. While the wettability times of tarhana samples containing olive leaf powder were short and statistically unaffected ($p > 0.05$), the increased solubility rate with higher olive leaf powder content aligns with the findings that specific ingredients can enhance water interaction properties. The high water-holding capacity and leafy structure of olive leaf powder likely contributed to these improved solubility characteristics. This suggests that ingredient selection plays a critical role in optimizing the functional properties of tarhana. There was no significant difference between the bulk and tapped density values of tarhana samples ($p > 0.05$). When the flowability and stickiness behavior of tarhanas is examined, it can be said that they have a very good level of flow and a low level of stickiness. This may be due to the low moisture content of tarhanas. Dadalı (2023) reported that the bulk and tapped density values of tarhana samples enriched with artichoke (*Cynara scolymus* L.) bracts

ranged from 454.76 to 506.27 kg m⁻³ and 589.51 to 616.61 kg m⁻³, respectively. Samples with artichoke bract enrichment (T10, T20, and T30) had lower bulk and tapped density values compared to the control, consistent with our findings for tarhana containing olive leaf powder. Similarly, Çalışkan-Koç and Özçira (2019) found that the bulk and tapped densities of tarhana samples enriched with wheat germ were 931.69–947.89 kg m⁻³ and 950.91–977.22 kg m⁻³, respectively. They also observed a significant decrease in tapped density values as the wheat germ substitution ratio increased, suggesting that enrichment with certain ingredients reduces the density of tarhana formulations. Notably, samples with lower bulk density occupy more space during packaging, which can influence storage and transportation considerations. Our findings

align with previous studies indicating that ingredient composition, such as olive leaf powder, artichoke bracts, or wheat germ, plays a critical role in influencing the bulk and tapped density of tarhana. The significantly lower bulk density observed in tarhana containing 10% olive leaf powder is consistent with the results of Dadalı (2023) and Çalışkan-Koç and Özçira (2019), suggesting that enrichment with fiber- and phytochemical-rich powders leads to a reduction in density. Additionally, the good flowability and low stickiness of all tarhana samples in our study further highlight the impact of low moisture content on these functional properties, reinforcing the importance of ingredient selection in optimizing tarhana formulation characteristics.

Table 2. The physicochemical, functional and powder properties of tarhana samples

Analysis	Samples				
	Control	TOLP-2.5	TOLP-5	TOLP-7.5	TOLP-10
Moisture Content (% _{wb})	6.28±0.59 ^c	8.24±0.55 ^{ab}	7.52±0.15 ^{ab}	8.37±0.21 ^a	8.40±0.84 ^a
Ash Content (% _{wb})	2.17±0.05 ^b	2.28±0.14 ^b	2.36±0.02 ^b	2.63±0.16 ^a	2.71±0.01 ^a
Water Holding Capacity (%)	32.50±3.54 ^d	37.50±0.71 ^c	46.50±0.71 ^b	48.50±3.54 ^b	59.00±2.83 ^a
Dispersibility (%)	28.19±2.69 ^a	22.79±3.51 ^b	19.12±4.70 ^{bc}	18.33±3.82 ^{bc}	15.80±0.02 ^{cd}
Wettability (s)	21.00±1.41 ^a	23.00±1.41 ^a	21.00±1.41 ^a	21.50±2.12 ^a	24.00±1.41 ^a
Solubility (s)	15.50±2.12 ^a	14.00±2.82 ^{ab}	13.00±1.41 ^b	11.00±1.41 ^{bc}	9.50±0.07 ^c
Bulk Density (kg/m ³)	917.43±0.00 ^a	917.43±0.00 ^a	917.43±0.00 ^a	917.43±0.00 ^a	921.68±6.01 ^a
Tapped Density (kg/m ³)	956.96±6.48 ^a	947.89±6.35 ^a	961.54±0.00 ^a	938.99±6.23 ^a	947.89±6.35 ^a
Flowability (CI)	4.13±0.65 ^a	3.21±0.65 ^{ab}	4.58±0.07 ^a	2.29±0.65 ^b	2.77±0.02 ^b
Cohesiveness (HR)	1.04±0.01 ^a	1.03±0.01 ^a	1.04±0.01 ^a	1.02±0.01 ^a	1.03±0.01 ^a

Control: Tarhana with 0% olive leaf powder; TOLP-2.5: Tarhana with 2.5% olive leaf powder; TOLP-5: Tarhana with 5% olive leaf powder; TOLP-7.5: Tarhana with 7.5% olive leaf powder; TOLP-10: Tarhana with 10% olive leaf powder. Different columns (a-e) in the same letters show the statistical difference (P<0.05).

3.3. Sensory evaluation

The effect of adding olive leaf powder to tarhana dough on sensory properties was investigated. The sensory characteristics of the samples, along with a radar chart depicting

consumer preference scores, are shown in Figure 3. Traditional tarhana typically has an orange-brown color. However, green coloration was observed in tarhana sample containing 5% or more olive leaf powder. The color scores of tarhana sample with 7.5% or

more olive leaf powder were lower than those of other samples, likely due to the increasing green color. Since the color scores of tarhana soups were above 4.1, it can be concluded that all samples were generally well-liked in terms of color. Tarhana is known for its sour odor. Except for samples containing 10% olive leaf powder, the odor scores of all tarhana samples were above 4. A proportional increase in the amount of olive leaf powder was associated with a noticeable decrease in consistency scores, both in the spoon and in the mouth. After drying, the tarhana dough was ground homogeneously into a powdered form, and tarhana soups were continuously stirred during preparation. However, panelists reported perceiving olive leaf particles as the concentration of olive leaf powder increased, which led to a lack of homogeneity in the soup. Consequently, the homogeneity scores of tarhanas containing olive leaf powder were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$). Tarhana soup typically has a sour, yeast-like flavor. As the

amount of olive leaf powder increased, the flavor scores declined. For samples with 7.5% or more olive leaf powder, the scores fell below 4. While panelists could not detect the presence of 2.5% olive leaf powder, they noted a foreign flavor in samples containing 5% or more, although they were unable to identify it as olive leaf powder. When examining the overall acceptability scores, the most preferred samples were the control and tarhanas containing 2.5% olive leaf powder. Interestingly, tarhanas with 2.5% olive leaf powder received scores comparable to, and in some cases higher than, the control sample. Tarhana containing 2.5% olive leaf powder was the most liked among the enriched samples, maintaining high sensory scores while introducing a mild enhancement. Increasing the olive leaf powder beyond 2.5% negatively affected color, flavor, and homogeneity, suggesting that 2.5% is an optimal level for consumer acceptance.

Figure 3. The radar chart of consumer preference scores of tarhana samples (Mean \pm SD, n=3)

4. Conclusion

This study has shown that the addition of olive leaf powder to tarhana formulation can exhibit significant physical, functional, powder, and sensory properties. All tarhana samples had moisture levels below the 10% threshold set by the Turkish standard. The ash

content (2.17-2.71%, wb) and water holding capacity (32.50-59.00%) of samples increased significantly with the addition of olive leaf powder ($p < 0.05$). Generally, the tarhana samples exhibited excellent flowability and a low level of stickiness. Overall, the sensory attribute scores of the tarhanas were found to be high up to a 7.5% olive leaf powder ratio.

The tarhana samples enriched with olive leaf powder, which has many health benefits, have been analyzed in terms of various characteristics, and valuable information has been shared. This is expected to shed light on other studies aimed at diversifying this traditional Turkish fermented food product. For future studies, it would be beneficial to investigate the impact of olive leaf powder on other important properties of tarhana, including its chemical composition, antioxidant activity, bioactive compound profile, and shelf life.

Declaration of Author Contributions

Emin Gülden; Investigation, Resources, Formal analysis, Selma Lubabe Erdoğan; Investigation, Resources, Formal analysis, Arda Akdoğan; Resources, Formal analysis, Methodology, Kadriye Altay; Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing. Gülşah Çalışkan Koç; Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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